

ON THE MONOTONICITY OF ADDITIVE REPRESENTATION FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

We study the monotonicity behavior of three (slightly) differently defined additive representation functions (as first considered by Erdős, Sárközy and Sós), answering one open question as well as another one partially, and give a slightly simpler proof for a result of Chen and Tang.

1. Introduction

For a set $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ of non-negative integers and every $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$ we define, using the notation $\text{card}(\mathcal{S}) = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} 1$ for a finite set \mathcal{S} ,

$$\begin{aligned} r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, b) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A} : a + b = n\}\right), \\ r_2(\mathcal{A}, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, b) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A} : a + b = n, a \leq b\}\right), \\ r_3(\mathcal{A}, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, b) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A} : a + b = n, a < b\}\right) \end{aligned}$$

as the additive representation functions r_1 , r_2 and r_3 belonging to \mathcal{A} , which count all solutions of the equation $a + b = n$ inside of \mathcal{A} with slightly more restrictions as the index of r increases.

Our starting point are three results of Erdős, Sárközy and Sós obtained in [4] (and a bit later improved by Balasubramanian in [1]) demonstrating the surprising different monotonicity behavior of r_1 , r_2 and r_3 :

Theorem 0 ([4]). *Let \mathcal{A} be an infinite set of positive integers.*

- (1) $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n)$ can be monotone from a certain point on, only if \mathcal{A} contains all the integers from a certain point on.
- (2) $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ cannot be monotone increasing from a certain point on, when

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \text{card}(\{1, \dots, N\} \setminus \mathcal{A}) / \log(N) = \infty.$$

- (3) *There is a set \mathcal{A} such that $\mathbb{N} \setminus \mathcal{A}$ is infinite and $r_3(\mathcal{A}, n)$ is monotone increasing for all $n \geq 0$.*

Later, in his collection of unsolved problems [5], Sárközy has asked with respect to property (1) of Theorem 0, whether or not one can find an infinite set $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{N}_0$ such that its upper asymptotic density is less than 1 and $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n)$ is monotone increasing for almost all n , which we can answer positively.

Theorem 1. *There exists an infinite set $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{N}_0$ such that its natural density is 0 and $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n)$ is monotone increasing almost everywhere:*

$$r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) \leq r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1)$$

holds for almost all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

In addition, we can also find a set $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{N}_0$ such that $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \mathcal{A}$ is infinite and $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n)$ is strictly monotone increasing almost everywhere:

$$r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) < r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1)$$

holds for almost all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Until today it remains unknown, whether or not there exists an infinite set \mathcal{A} such that $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ is monotone increasing from a certain point on, although more and more conditions have been collected (as in [2] or [3]) under which $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ cannot be monotone increasing. On the other hand, in their paper [4] Erdős, Sárközy and Sós noted that perhaps a similar construction of a set \mathcal{A} as the one for property (3) in Theorem 0 is also possible for $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$, however we can prove this is not possible in the following sense.

Theorem 2. *If $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{N}_0$ is non-empty and $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \mathcal{A}$ is infinite, then $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ cannot be monotone increasing for all $n \geq 0$.*

Finally, we give an alternative proof of the following result by Chen and Tang [3], in which we do not need property (1) of Theorem 0 for $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n)$ anymore.

Theorem 3 ([3]). *If $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{N}_0$, then $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ (or $r_3(\mathcal{A}, n)$, resp.) cannot be strictly monotone increasing from a certain point on.*

We would like to mention that illustrating the pairs (a, b) from $\mathbb{N}_0 \times \mathbb{N}_0$ as points $(a + b, a)$ in the plane, such that the corresponding points of all pairs with the same sum $a + b = n$ are on one vertical line, has been helpful in finding our proofs, where for an integer $c \geq 0$ not in \mathcal{A} we then remove all points (c, x) and (x, c) with $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$ lying on two certain lines.

2. Proofs

Before we start with the proofs of all theorems, let us quickly collect the following helpful formulas for r_1, r_2 and r_3 in the special case $\mathcal{A} = \mathbb{N}_0$.

Lemma 1. *For $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, we have*

- (1) $r_1(\mathbb{N}_0, n) = n + 1,$
- (2) $r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, n) = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1,$
- (3) $r_3(\mathbb{N}_0, n) = \lfloor (n - 1)/2 \rfloor + 1,$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ denotes the largest integer not exceeding $x \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof. By definition we have

$$r_1(\mathbb{N}_0, n) = \text{card}\left(\{(a, n - a) : a \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}\}\right) = n + 1,$$

and if $n = 2m$ ($m \in \mathbb{N}_0$) is even, we find

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, n - a) : a \in \mathbb{N}_0, a \leq n/2 = m\}\right) = m + 1, \\ r_3(\mathbb{N}_0, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, n - a) : a \in \mathbb{N}_0, a < n/2 = m\}\right) = m, \end{aligned}$$

or when $n = 2m + 1$ is odd, then

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, n - a) : a \in \mathbb{N}_0, a \leq n/2 = m + 1/2\}\right) = m + 1, \\ r_3(\mathbb{N}_0, n) &= \text{card}\left(\{(a, n - a) : a \in \mathbb{N}_0, a < n/2 = m + 1/2\}\right) = m + 1, \end{aligned}$$

and both cases together also lead us to the formulas (2) and (3). □

Proof of Theorem 1. First, let us choose $\mathcal{A} = \{2^i : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ whose natural density

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\text{card}(\mathcal{A} \cap \{1, \dots, N\})}{N} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor}{N} \leq \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log_2 N}{N} = 0$$

does exist and equals 0. Out of the $\lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor$ members of \mathcal{A} up to $N \geq 1$ we can build no more than $(\log_2 N)^2$ pairwise sums, or in other words, there are at least $N - (\log_2 N)^2$ positive integers $n \leq N$ such that

$$r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) = 0 \leq r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1).$$

Thus, the probability that a positive integer n which is chosen at random satisfies $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) \leq r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1)$ is at least

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N - (\log_2 N)^2}{N} = 1 - \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(\log_2 N)^2}{N} = 1 - 0 = 1,$$

as desired.

Now, let us choose $\mathcal{A} = \mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{2^i : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ whose natural density is $1 - 0 = 1$, and define the family of sets $\mathcal{A}_j = \mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{2^i : i \in \mathbb{N}, i \leq j\}$, where for $j \in \mathbb{N}$ we only have removed the first j powers of 2.

If $n \in \{2^j + 1, 2^j + 2, \dots, 2^{j+1}\}$, we have

$$r_1(\mathcal{A}_{j-1}, n) = r_1(\mathbb{N}_0, n) - 2 \cdot (j - 1) = n + 1 - 2 \cdot (j - 1)$$

since $a + b \leq 2^{j-1} + 2^{j-1} = 2^j < n$ for any a and b in $\{2^i : i \in \mathbb{N}, i \leq j - 1\}$. Moreover, if n is also not of the form $2^j + 2^i$ with $i \in \mathbb{N}$ ($i \leq j$), we even find

$$r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) = r_1(\mathcal{A}_j, n) = r_1(\mathcal{A}_{j-1}, n) - 2 = n + 1 - 2 \cdot j$$

(while $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) = n + 1 - 2 \cdot (j - 1)$ in case of $n = 2^j + 2^i$) together with

$$\begin{aligned} r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1) &= r_1(\mathcal{A}_j, n + 1) \\ &\geq r_1(\mathbb{N}_0, n + 1) - 2 \cdot j \\ &= (n + 1) + 1 - 2 \cdot j > r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) \end{aligned}$$

as long as $n + 1 < 2^{j+1}$, and since there are no more than j numbers of the form $2^j + 2^i$ from $2^j + 1$ up to $2^{j+1} - 2$, we have found at least $2^j - 2 - j$ numbers n in $\{2^j + 1, 2^j + 2, \dots, 2^{j+1}\}$ such that $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) < r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1)$.

In view of the partition

$$\mathbb{N} = \{1, 2\} \cup \bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} \{2^j + 1, 2^j + 2, \dots, 2^{j+1}\},$$

up to an integer $N \geq 1$ we then find at most

$$\begin{aligned} &2 + \sum_{j=1}^{\lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor + 1} (2 + j) \\ &\leq 2 + (\lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor + 1) \cdot (2 + \lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor + 1) \leq 2 + (\log_2 N + 3)^2 \end{aligned}$$

numbers n such that $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) \geq r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1)$. Thus, this time the probability that a positive integer n chosen at random satisfies $r_1(\mathcal{A}, n) < r_1(\mathcal{A}, n + 1)$ is again at least

$$\begin{aligned} &\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N - (2 + (\log_2 N + 3)^2)}{N} \\ &= 1 - \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{(\log_2 N)^2}{N} + \frac{6 \log_2 N}{N} + \frac{11}{N} \right) = 1 - (0 + 0 + 0) = 1, \end{aligned}$$

as desired. □

Proof of Theorem 2. Let c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots denote the elements of $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \mathcal{A}$ in increasing order. If $c_1 = 2m + 1$ ($m \in \mathbb{N}_0$) is odd, then

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 - 1) &= r_2(\mathcal{A} \cap \{0, 1, \dots, c_1 - 1\}, c_1 - 1) \\ &= r_2(\{0, 1, \dots, c_1 - 1\}, c_1 - 1) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_1 - 1) = \lfloor (2m + 1 - 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 = m + 1, \end{aligned}$$

while on the other side

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1) &= r_2(\mathcal{A} \cap \{0, 1, \dots, c_1 - 1, c_1\}, c_1) \\ &= r_2(\{0, 1, \dots, c_1 - 1\}, c_1) = r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1\}, c_1) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_1) - 1 = \lfloor (2m + 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 1 = m. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, there would be a decrease $r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 - 1) > r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1)$, which means c_1 has to be even. At this point, we distinguish two cases for c_1 .

Case 1: $c_1 = 2x$ for $x > 0$.

If the next number $c_2 = 2m + 1$ ($m \geq x$) missing from \mathcal{A} is odd, then

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_2 - 1) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1\}, c_2 - 1) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_2 - 1) - 1 = \lfloor (2m + 1 - 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 1 = m, \end{aligned}$$

while due to $c_1 + c_2 \neq c_2$ ($c_1 > 0$) we get

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_2) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2\}, c_2) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_2) - 2 = \lfloor (2m + 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 2 = m - 1. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, again there would be a decrease $r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_2 - 1) > r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_2)$, which means c_2 has to be even, and we write $c_2 = 2y$ ($y > x$).

Assume for a moment that c_3 is larger than $c_1 + c_2 + 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 + c_2) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2\}, c_1 + c_2) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_1 + c_2) - 1 \\ &= \lfloor (2x + 2y)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 1 \\ &= x + y, \end{aligned}$$

while due to $c_1 + c_2 \neq c_1 + c_2 + 1$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 + c_2 + 1) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2\}, c_1 + c_2 + 1) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_1 + c_2 + 1) - 2 \\ &= \lfloor (2x + 2y + 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 2 \\ &= x + y - 1. \end{aligned}$$

The discovered decrease $r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 + c_2) > r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 + c_2 + 1)$ even remains as long as $c_3 > c_2 + 1$, because here

$$(c_1 + c_2) - c_i < (c_1 + c_2 + 1) - c_i \leq (c_1 + c_2 + 1) - c_3 < c_1$$

for $i \geq 3$, which means $(c_1 + c_2) - c_i$ and $(c_1 + c_2 + 1) - c_i$ are not in $\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \mathcal{A}$. Now, when c_j is the largest integer less than $c_1 + c_2 + 2$ missing from \mathcal{A} , then

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 + c_2) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_j\}, c_1 + c_2) \\ &\geq r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_1 + c_2) - 1 - (j - 2) \\ &= \lfloor (2x + 2y)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 1 - (j - 2) \\ &= x + y - j + 2, \end{aligned}$$

while due to $c_1 + c_2 \neq c_1 + c_2 + 1$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_1 + c_2 + 1) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_j\}, c_1 + c_2 + 1) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_1 + c_2 + 1) - 2 - (j - 2) \\ &= \lfloor (2x + 2y + 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 2 - (j - 2) \\ &= x + y - j + 1. \end{aligned}$$

In order to avoid this decrease all that remains is the choice $c_3 = c_2 + 1$. But then we discover the unavoidable decrease from

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_2) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2\}, c_2) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_2) - 2 \\ &= \lfloor 2y/2 \rfloor + 1 - 2 = y - 1 \end{aligned}$$

(note that $c_1 + c_2 \geq 2 + c_2 > c_2$) to

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, c_2 + 1) &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0 \setminus \{c_1, c_2, c_3\}, c_2 + 1) \\ &= r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, c_2 + 1) - 3 \\ &= \lfloor (2y + 1)/2 \rfloor + 1 - 3 = y - 2 \end{aligned}$$

(note that $c_2 + c_3 > c_1 + c_3 > c_1 + c_2 \geq 2 + c_2 > c_2 + 1$).

Case 2: $c_1 = 0$.

In this case, when $m > 0$ denotes the minimum of \mathcal{A} , we can write

$$\begin{aligned} r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2m + n) &= r_2(\mathcal{A} \cap \{m + 0, m + 1, \dots, m + n\}, 2m + n) \\ &= r_2((\mathcal{A} - m) \cap \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, n) \\ &= r_2(\mathcal{A} - m, n) \end{aligned}$$

for all $n \geq 0$, where for the set $\mathcal{A} - m = \{a - m : a \in \mathcal{A}\}$ (in place of \mathcal{A}) we have already shown in the first case one can find some n such that

$$r_2(\mathcal{A} - m, n) > r_2(\mathcal{A} - m, n + 1).$$

By the just found link, this in turn also leads to

$$r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2m + n) > r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2m + n + 1),$$

and so we have found a decrease in any case. □

Proof of Theorem 3. Let us suppose there exists an integer N such that $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ is strictly monotone increasing for $n \geq N$. But then from this point onwards $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ grows by at least one whenever n increases by one, and thus at $n = 2N + 3$ we find

$$r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2N + 3) \geq r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2N + 2) + 1 \geq \cdots \geq r_2(\mathcal{A}, N) + 1 \cdot (N + 3) \geq N + 3$$

in contradiction to

$$r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2N + 3) \leq r_2(\mathbb{N}_0, 2N + 3) = \lfloor (2N + 3)/2 \rfloor + 1 \leq N + 5/2$$

due to Lemma 1 from before. Therefore, all that remains is that $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$ cannot be strictly monotone increasing from a certain point on. Similarly, we can also show (by replacing r_2 with r_3 in the first chain of inequalities, and then noting $r_3(\mathcal{A}, n)$ never exceeds $r_2(\mathcal{A}, n)$, so we have $r_3(\mathcal{A}, 2N + 3) \leq r_2(\mathcal{A}, 2N + 3)$ in the other one) that $r_3(\mathcal{A}, n)$ cannot be strictly monotone increasing from a certain point on. \square

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